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“THE FIRE THAT FORGED ME”

I grew up in a house of silence and sound,
Where bottles clinked more than kind words found.
My father – distressed, a storm in the night,
Yet sharp as a blade when his mind caught the light.

His genius was buried in liquor and pain,
A brilliance clouded by thunder and rain.
While my mother, a warrior in borrowed grace,
Chased lenders with tears tracing her face.

She patched up my dreams with coins she could find,
Every peso a prayer, every debt a bind.
Yet I stood, through it all, with my books held tight,
Learning to grow in the absence of light.

And I rose – oh I rose – with scars on my skin,
But each one a story of strength held within.
I grabbed the DOST like a lifeline of flame,
Burning through shadows that whispered by name.

Four years I battled, but I never fell,
Carved out a future where none dared dwell.
And now, crowned with the title I yearned –
A licensed teacher, a respect I earned.

So judge not the roots from which I began,
For I am the proof of how far one can span.
From pain I was planted, from grit I was spun,
The fire that forged me is the reason I won.